

Synergy of Financial Literacy and Marketing Digitalization to Support the Sustainability of Wayang Kulit Msmes in Bali

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ABSTRACT: This Community Service Program (PKM) was carried out at the Balinese Puppet UKM owned by Mr. Purwa Yasa which is located in Banjar Semana, Mambal Village, Abianseml District, Badung Regency, Bali. These SMEs have an important role in preserving local culture as well as developing the creative economy. However, based on observations, it was found that the main problems faced by partners were the limitations in the aspect of financial management and the lack of optimal use of digital marketing. Partners still use manual financial recording that is not systematic, making it difficult to manage cash flow and access to capital. In addition, marketing strategies are still conventional through exhibitions or word-of-mouth promotions, so market reach is limited. This PKM activity aims to improve the financial literacy of partners, develop digital marketing strategies, and strengthen business competitiveness to be more sustainable. The methods used include lectures, training, and assistance related to simple financial records, separation of business and personal finances, and the use of sales memorandum to accurately determine turnover. In addition, digital marketing training is carried out through the use of social media such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram, accompanied by the creation of product catalogs and promotional content. The results of the activity show an increase in partners' understanding of simple financial management, with the implementation of daily cash recording, sales notes, and more structured monthly reports. In terms of marketing, partners are starting to actively use social media as a means of promotion, so that wayang kulit products are better known to the wider community. With this program, it is hoped that Balinese Wayang Kulit SMEs can be more professional in business management, increase turnover, and be able to contribute to the preservation of local culture and economy.

KEYWORDS: community service, Balinese puppetry, financial literacy, digital marketing, MSMEs

I. INTRODUCTION

Balinese people are known to have creativity and high skills in making unique products, one of which is Balinese puppetry which displays the characters and philosophies of local culture. The Balinese puppet industry is an important part of the handicraft sector that supports the economic growth of the Balinese people. This carved puppet is not only used as an architectural element in art parties and exhibitions, but also an attraction for local and foreign tourists. Along with the increase in tourist visits and interest in Balinese culture, the demand for Balinese puppet products also continues to grow. Many handicraft businesses in Bali, including in several villages that are handicraft centers, are now competing to create more varied puppet products, still prioritize quality, and maintain the characteristics of Balinese carvings. With stable market demand, the puppet industry in Bali not only supports the tourism sector, but also contributes to improving the welfare of the people and the overall economy of Bali.

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) have a strategic role in the Indonesian economy, especially in the preservation of local culture. One of the sectors that contributes to maintaining cultural heritage is the Balinese puppet craft industry. In Abianseml, Badung, there are several business actors who still maintain traditional puppet making. However, despite having high artistic and cultural values, this venture faces challenges in managerial and marketing aspects. Geographically, Abianseml is one of the sub-districts in Badung Regency that has cultural and tourism potential. With its proximity to tourist areas such as Ubud and Kuta, handicraft products such as wayang kulit should have a great opportunity to develop. However, data shows that many puppet artisans still face limitations in financial management and digital marketing.

One of the main problems faced by puppet business actors in Abianseml is the lack of systematic financial records. Many business actors do not understand the importance of simple financial records, making it difficult to control cash flow and determine business development strategies. According to recent research [1], good financial records can increase the resilience of MSMEs to business risks and improve their access to capital. In addition, information technology can play an important role in supporting a more effective and efficient financial recording system [2]. According to [3], accurate financial recording allows MSMEs to have better control over cash flow, better financial planning, and increase the chances of getting banking or investor

Synergy of Financial Literacy and Marketing Digitalization to Support the Sustainability of Wayang Kulit Msmes in Bali

support. This is in line with the findings [4] which state that transparent financial recording can increase business credibility in the eyes of stakeholders

MSMEs in Bali, especially in the Abiansemal area, have developed from the past to the present. The people of Abiansemal, especially Balinese carving craftsmen, have found potential business opportunities, one of which is through puppet crafts run by Mr. Nyoman Purwa Yasa. This MSME is located on Jalan Raya Semana, Mambal, Abiansemal Bali, and offers Balinese Leather Wayang making services from Cowhide with Balinese carving motifs. The owner of Wayang kulit Pak Nyoman began to learn the art of carving since high school from his uncle, which made him delve deeper into the world of carving. Armed with high skills and interest in carving, he finally decided to open a Balinese Wayang Kulit business. The motifs and philosophies contained in Balinese Wayang Kulit are full of cultural and spiritual meanings that are closely related to the life of the Balinese people. Each carving has distinctive motifs that not only serve as decorations, but also convey noble values and a deep philosophy of life. Initially, Mr. Purwa Yasa marketed his products from word of mouth, now with the development of the marketing era, it is done using *WhatsApp* and *face books*.

In terms of finances, management is still carried out by the owner personally. Recording of expenses and income is also still being done by the owner, so records regarding expenses and income from sales are not detailed and tend to be unstable. To help the production process, Mr. Purwa Yasa recruited 4 employees who already have skills and duties, each of which has the following tasks. 1). Two people play a role in choosing raw materials, so that the raw materials obtained are of good quality. 2). Two people play a role in the production, namely carving, polishing, and painting the pernish (finishing). The raw materials used are dried cowhide leather, sandpaper, thinner paint, chisel. The equipment used is paint brushes, cutters, chisels and chisel hammers.

Another challenge that partners face is the lack of marketing optimization through social media. In today's digital age, the use of platforms like Instagram, and TikTok is essential in reaching a wider market. However, many artisans still rely on conventional marketing through exhibitions or direct visits, so they do not take advantage of the potential of digital marketing [5]. Service-based marketing is one of the important approaches in digital marketing strategies to improve customer interaction and satisfaction [6]. Without an effective marketing strategy, wayang kulit products are difficult to compete with other cultural products that are better known to tourists. Consumer behavior in the digital era is also a factor that must be considered. According to [7], consumers tend to search for product information online before making a purchase. Therefore, the use of digital marketing strategies based on understanding consumer behavior is essential to increase product competitiveness. According to [8] emphasizes that digital marketing can increase product exposure and allow for better interaction between producers and consumers. In addition, a study from [9] shows that digital-based marketing strategies can increase customer loyalty and expand market reach for MSMEs. According to [10], the use of *e-commerce* and digital marketing allows MSMEs to compete more effectively in the global market at a lower cost than conventional marketing.

Based on these existing conditions, a strategy to strengthen MSMEs is needed through the implementation of simple financial recording and social media optimization. With the right intervention, it is hoped that puppet business actors can improve operational efficiency, expand market share, and support the sustainability of their business in preserving local cultural heritage. Based on the results of the survey on wayang kulit product partners, it is presented in the following figure:

Figure 1

Synergy of Financial Literacy and Marketing Digitalization to Support the Sustainability of Wayang Kulit Msme in Bali

II. PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

2.1 Problems and solutions.

- 1). Financial aspects. Lack of Financial Literacy: Lack of knowledge about financial management makes it impossible for partners to develop a mature budget plan and effective financial strategy. Often partners do not separate personal and business finances, and do not have neat bookkeeping, making it difficult to monitor cash flow and business financial health.
- 2). Marketing aspect. Partners often struggle to expand their market reach due to network and information limitations, yet to leverage digital technologies such as e-commerce and social media to market their products widely.

2.2 Solutions offered

To overcome these problems, this service program offers several strategic solutions that are tailored to the proposer's field of science, including:

1. Financial Aspect Solutions Provide basic financial literacy training, including simple financial recording, separation of personal and business finances, and preparation of budget plans. Assistance in the use of simple bookkeeping to make it easier to monitor cash flow and financial statements.
 2. Marketing Aspect Solutions. Training in digital-based marketing strategies through the use of social media, *e-commerce*, and other online platforms. Assistance in creating attractive promotional content and according to market trends.
- With the implementation of these solutions, it is hoped that partners will be able to increase managerial capacity, expand marketing access, so that the business run can be more sustainable, adaptive, and highly competitive

III. METHODS AND FIVE STAGES OF SERVICE IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 The implementation method used in Balinese puppet puppet SME partners is the method of lectures, training and procurement of appropriate technological equipment.

- 1) The lecture is in the form of counseling on the importance of accounting for a business and the importance of business promotion in increasing sales turnover. In this activity, the participants were given material on the role of accounting for the development of a business
- 2) Training is related to providing training to partner members on how to record transactions using sales memorandums so as to obtain the actual total turnover
- 3) Procurement of Appropriate Technology Equipment with the help of large bucket equipment to speed up production poses and increase production capacity

Product catalog, business cards and special product hampers boxes. Evaluation of the implementation of community service activities with the community partnership empowerment scheme can be carried out by 1) Initial evaluation. 2) Final evaluation 3) Program Sustainability Evaluation

Table 1. Indicate the stages of activities and types of activities at each stage.

Table 1

Stages and types of activities

Phase	Types of activities
Socialization	Partners are given counseling on the importance of accounting for a business
Training	Partners are given how to record ransaks using notes.
Application of Technology	Application of technology in creating product catalogs, label design and business accounts
Mentoring	Assistance in using technology in designing media product catalogs Online and take notes.
Program Sustainability	Conduct an evaluation by distributing a questionnaire to find out the partner's ability after service activities are held.

3.2 The five stages in Community Service are as follows:

1) Preparation and Observation Stage

At this stage, field observations are first carried out on the Partner to obtain information and find out the real situation or condition of the Partner so that the most urgent problems of the partner can be found for a solution through assistance.

2) Implementation Stage

In the second stage, mentoring began to be carried out by providing counseling, lectures on solutions that must be done by partners to overcome problems

Synergy of Financial Literacy and Marketing Digitalization to Support the Sustainability of Wayang Kulit Msmes in Bali

3) Evaluation/Monitoring Stage

At this stage, after assistance in the form of training, an evaluation is carried out to determine the development of the partner whether there is positive progress in terms of understanding the material provided and the increasing progress on the products sold.

4) Report Preparation Stage At this stage, the team prepares a report on the results of the implementation of service which will later be evaluated by the review team for the refinement of the final report

5) Deposit Status Report

At this stage, it is the submission of the Final report which includes a report on the results of the implementation of service in the form of outputs that have been published in a journal, videos of publication activities on online or print media and IPR

IV RESULTS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ACTIVITIES

The results of the implementation during the PKM process of the PKM activities of Wayang Kulit Banjar Semana Mambal Abiansemal Badung. This PKM activity involved 3 lecturers and 4 students as a PKM implementation team with different expertise. It began with the acceptance of the PKM implementation team by SME partners kawé-kawé. In this activity, Mr. Nyoman Purwa Yasa's partner explained how the conditions and resources he manages in running a tofu business. The next activity is counseling and training activities by the PKM implementation team. The first counseling began with material on the importance of accounting in business activities presented by the PKM Team, that accounting is an important factor in improving business activities. With accounting, business actors, in this case SME partners, can immediately find out about business developments effectively and efficiently. When the business is still small or micro-scale, accounting recording can be done simply through sales notes. No less interesting is the importance of separating records between entities and personal interests, so that the partner's financial data does not blend with the family's financial data. Next, partners are given training on how to keep simple bookkeeping. This training on how to record books in a simple way begins with recording all daily sales transactions in the prepared cash receipt book, then for transactions that use the order system or orders are recorded in a complete and clear sales note starting from the date of the transaction, the item of goods sold and the selling price. Especially for cash expenditure transactions related to the purchase of materials, equipment and so on, it is also recorded in the cash expenditure book that has been provided.

The next counseling activity carried out by the PKM Team is related to the importance of marketing to support the market area so that consumers increase and sales turnover can increase, it is very important to establish cooperation with financial institutions such as cooperatives or LPDs of local customary villages to make it easier to borrow capital. *Face Book* and *WhatsApp*. *Product photos are made in one product catalog*. *The promotional program received a warm welcome from partners, considering that promotions with this model are simple, with the hope that the Partner's name will become more known. Business promotion programs, can easily remember the name of the product and also the telephone number, making it easier to place an order*

The following is shown the implementation of the service and the results such as

The following pictures;

Synergy of Financial Literacy and Marketing Digitalization to Support the Sustainability of Wayang Kulit Msmes in Bali

Figure 2 Product Catalog

https://www.instagram.com/manik_suling_collection?igsh=MWU3YnIyMzFqZ3dmcw==

<https://youtube.com/@maniksuling3305?si=cs0KFJtnWN8nDvSF>

Synergy of Financial Literacy and Marketing Digitalization to Support the Sustainability of Wayang Kulit Msmes in Bali

Image 3 Instagram and youtube MSMEs manik sulin wayang BAL

Figure 3. Financial Recording Documentation

After the assistance was carried out, there were several benefits obtained, namely Partners have more skills in making daily cash books to record expenses and all incoming income, partners are able to carry out online marketing, as well as increase market share Based on the data in Table 1, it can be seen from the asset value that increased by 50%, sales increased by 60% so that the benefits of PKM were felt by partners

Table .1 Activity Achievement Indicators

Yes	Information	Before PKM	After PKM	Progress
1.	Asset	20 million	30 million	+/- 50 %
2.	Average turnover/month	10 million	16 million	+/-60 %

This PKM activity ended by providing assistance in the form of laser cutting machine equipment, product catalogs and business cards, This assistance was handed over directly by the Head of the PKM Team to Mr. Nyoman Purwa Yasa, Hopefully with the provision of this assistance it can increase the productivity of sales results so that it can increase profits. Based on the data in the table above, it is clear that the progress of the value of assets has increased by 50% and the average sales per month have increased by 60% After SMEs carried out the mentoring process, some positive changes immediately occurred: Finances are more organized , SMEs are starting to have better financial reports. Increase production with more efficient methods, production increases. Wider marketing , SMEs are starting to actively market their products online and offline. The long-term impact of this program includes: Increasing the Competitiveness of SMEs in kawekawek to become more competitive in the market. Increased Profitability, Increased Turnover due to more effective marketing. Sustainability SME businesses can survive in the long run with a better strategy. Improved Well-Being Income increases, family economy is more stable

Figure 4 Equipment handover documentation

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the activities that have been carried out, the following conclusions and suggestions can be drawn:

5.1 Conclusion

1. The PKM program has succeeded in increasing the motivation of partners in developing their businesses through the use of human resource potential and the implementation of the right business strategy.
2. Partners are able to expand their marketing reach by implementing digital marketing strategies, including promotion through social media.
3. Partners understand the importance of simple financial records so that they can know the position of the business in profit/loss conditions and make more appropriate decisions.
4. There was a significant increase in business performance, as shown by a 50% increase in assets and a 60% increase in turnover after the mentoring program

5.2 Suggestions

Mentoring activities should be continued on an ongoing basis, especially related to the preparation of financial statements, calculation of cost of production, and digital marketing strategies. Thus, *Wayang Kulit* MSMEs can be more competitive and able to develop markets at the local and regional levels. After the completion of the implementation of this PKM, the Partners and the PKM Team hope that there will still be a good relationship and readiness from the PKM Team to help if there are problems in the implementation, for example, problems with the preparation of financial statements, the preparation of Profit and Loss reports and the calculation of cost of production to increase revenue

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